

DETERMINANTS OF TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY IN POTATO PRODUCTION: EVIDENCE FROM SAMARKAND REGION, UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the technical efficiency of potato-producing farms in the Samarkand region of Uzbekistan using farm-level cross-sectional data from 121 households. A stochastic frontier approach (SFA) with a Cobb–Douglas production function was applied to estimate the effects of key inputs - including seed quantity, organic and chemical fertilizers, and labor - on potato yield. Results show that average technical efficiency is approximately 0.85, indicating that farms could increase output by 15% using existing resources and technology. The study highlights the need for optimized input use, improved seed quality, and better management practices to enhance potato productivity in Uzbekistan.

Introduction. The agricultural sector plays a crucial role in ensuring food security and economic stability in Uzbekistan, with potato cultivation being a significant component of this sector (Karimov A., 2014; ADB, 2021). Given the strategic importance of this crop, understanding the technical efficiency of potato farmers and the factors influencing it is paramount for optimizing resource utilization and enhancing overall agricultural productivity (Babakholov, Sh, 2024). This study aims to address this by analyzing the technical efficiency of potato farms in Samarkand region and identifying the determinants that contribute to observed efficiency levels, thereby supporting sustainable agricultural development in the country (Khamraeva & Ochilova, 2023). Globally, improving agricultural productivity is crucial for sustaining a growing population and reducing the ecological footprint of expanding cultivation into new lands (Solis et al., 2009; FAO, 2022). One critical pathway to achieving this productivity growth without expanding land use is through the enhancement of technical efficiency, which allows for increased output with the same level of resource inputs (Liu et. al., 2019). In the context of potato farming, this involves ensuring that farmers utilize their existing resources—land, labor, capital, and technology—as effectively as possible to maximize potato yields. This research, therefore, seeks to evaluate the current technical efficiency levels among potato cultivators in Samarkand region, a key agricultural hub in Uzbekistan, to identify specific areas for improvement in resource allocation and management practices.

Methodology. This study investigates to calculate technical efficiency of potato-cultivating farms and then to identify determinants of technical efficiency. We employ two-stage empirical approach to identify these relationships. First, Cobb-Douglas stochastic

frontier function used to identify current state of farms' technical efficiency. Then Tobit regression was employed to investigate what factors influence farms' technical efficiency.

Scholars actively employ 2 methods for calculation of technical efficiency: stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) and nonparametric Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). DEA model is criticized for not taking into account measurement errors. SFA model could solve this problem, as in this model error term is separated to 2 components: technical inefficiency and statistical noise (Coelli et al., 2005; Kumbhakar et al., 2003).

In our study, we include 5 inputs in model: seed quantity (kg), chemical fertilizer (kg), organic fertilizer (kg), and labor (man-days). The dependant variable is potato yield in kilogram. The production function is specified as:

$$\ln(Y_i) = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^4 (\beta_k * \ln(X_{ki})) + v_i - u_i$$

Where:

- Y_i = output (total wheat production in kg) of the i-th farm
- X_{ki} = quantity of the k-th input used by the i-th farm
- β_k = parameters to be estimated
- v_i = two-sided random error term, $v_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$
- u_i = non-negative inefficiency term, $u_i \sim N^+(0, \sigma_u^2)$

The inefficiency component u_i captures the shortfall of actual output from the potential frontier output, given the input levels. Technical efficiency (TE) for each farm is calculated as:

$$TE_i = \frac{Y_i}{Y_i^*} = \exp(-u_i)$$

Where:

- Y_i = observed output
- Y_i^* = frontier (maximum possible) output given inputs

$TE_i \in [0,1]$, with values closer to 1 indicating higher efficiency

After identifying technical efficiency scores of farms, we employ Tobit regression model to examine factors of farm-level technical efficiency. The latent Tobit model is specified as:

$$TE_i^* = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 ESI_i + \gamma_2 X_1 + \gamma_3 X_2 + \gamma_4 X_3 + \gamma_5 X_4 + \gamma_6 X_5 + \gamma_7 X_6 + \gamma_8 X_7 + \gamma_9 X_8 + \varepsilon_i \quad \varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

Where:

TE_i^* = latent (unobserved) technical efficiency score for the i-th farm

$TE_i = TE_i^*$ IF $0 < TE_i^* < 1$; otherwise, it is censored at the bounds

ESI_i = Environmental sustainability index for the i-th farm

X_1 = Age

X_2 = Access to credit

X_3 = Cluster membership

X_4 = Participation in trainings

X_5 = Distance to market

$i = 1, 2, \dots, 121$

Results and discussion.

Descriptive statistics. This section presents descriptive statistics of the main variables used in the analysis. Table 1 reports summary statistics for a sample of 121 potato-cultivating farmers from Samarkand region. The data show substantial variation in land size, input use, and labor allocation, reflecting the heterogeneity of production systems in the region.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of key variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Potato yield per ha (kg)	28544.31	8107.6	6000	50000
Potato land (ha)	3.55	3.27	0.5	18
Seed used (kg)	4015.5	715.9	1	8
Organic Fertilizer (kg)	23256.2	8893.4	2000	38000
Chemical Fertilizer (kg)	1071.9	470.7	300	2000
Labor (man-days)	143.4	31.8	90	236
Farmers' Age (years)	44.7	10.25	23	75
Access to credit	0.496	0.5	0	1
Cluster Membership (binary)	0.504	0.502	0	1
Training participation	0.529	0.501	0	1
Distance to market	0.88	0.8	0	2
Number of observations	121			

These figures suggest that average yield of potato is 28544 kilogram, while average land of potato cultivated is 3.55 hectares. Farmers' average age is 46 years and they use 4015.5 kilogram of potato seed on average. Roughly 50% of farmers is cluster members and 52.9 % of farmers participate in trainings related to potato cultivation methods.

According to SFA model, average technical efficiency of potato-growing farmers is 0.84 coefficient. This means, farmers can increase their productivity with optimally using the current resources. Figure 1 below describes histogram of technical efficiency scores of farmers. From the given figure, we can conclude that most of the farmers technical efficiency scores lie between 0.75-0.95 range. And very few farmers technical efficiency scores are between 0.2-0.65. And one can see that any of the farmers reach full efficiency in the sample.

Figure 1. Histogram of farmers technical efficiency scores.

In second stage, the determinants of farms' technical efficiency scores analyzed with Tobit regression model. According to model results, table 2 reports the factors influencing technical efficiency among potato producers. The overall model is significant (LR $\chi^2(6)=47.47$, $p<0.001$), indicating that the included variables jointly explain efficiency differences. The Environmental Sustainability Index shows a positive effect on efficiency (0.0865, $p<0.10$), meaning farms with better soil and resource management perform more efficiently. Farmer age has no significant impact. Cluster membership negatively affects efficiency (-0.0801 , $p<0.01$), suggesting that contract or cluster arrangements may impose coordination constraints that reduce performance.

Table 2. Tobit model estimating technical efficiency determinants

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error
Environmental Sustainability Index	0.086**	0.047
Age	0.0017	0.0012
Cluster membership	-0.08***	0.027
Training participation	0.077***	0.028
Access to credit	0.071**	0.027
Distance to market	0.03*	0.017
Constant	0.58***	0.065

Note: *** $p<0.01$, ** $p<0.05$, * $p<0.1$

Model statistics: LR $\chi^2(6) = 47.47$, Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0561$, Observations = 121

In contrast, participation in training significantly improves efficiency (0.0765, $p<0.01$), highlighting the importance of extension and knowledge transfer. Access to credit also raises efficiency (0.0714, $p<0.05$), confirming that financial constraints hinder optimal input use. Distance to market has a positive but marginal effect (0.0301, $p<0.10$), possibly reflecting stronger cost discipline or specialization among more remote farms. Overall, sustainability practices, training, and credit access enhance efficiency, while cluster participation lowers it, and age plays no meaningful role.

Conclusion. This study examined the technical efficiency of potato-producing farms in the Samarkand region and identified the key factors shaping efficiency outcomes. The analysis shows that although farms operate at a relatively high average efficiency level, substantial potential remains to improve performance within existing resource and technology constraints. The results indicate that environmentally sustainable farming practices, participation in training programs, and access to credit significantly and positively influence technical efficiency. These findings underscore the importance of strengthening extension services, promoting sustainability-oriented practices, and expanding financial inclusion to support more efficient production. Conversely, cluster membership is associated with lower efficiency, suggesting that the current structure and management arrangements within agricultural clusters may require reassessment to better align incentives and reduce coordination burdens on farmers. Farmer age does not appear to play a meaningful role in shaping efficiency differences. Overall, the study highlights that improving managerial capacity, ensuring access to key services and finance, and refining institutional arrangements are crucial pathways to raising productivity in potato farming in the region.

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